

VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE : COMPARISON BETWEEN A SELF-CONSISTENT MODEL AND EXPERIMENTAL DATA

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a method is proposed to determine the viscoelastic behaviour of unidirectional fibre-reinforced composites. The method is based on the N. Laws and R. Mc Laughlin model. The discrepancy between the experimental data and the estimate observed involves to modify the model in order to consider the non-linearity of the matrix and the problem of the weak interface between fibre and matrix. The study are performed on glass-epoxy materials.

1. INTRODUCTION

Unidirectional composite materials, made from fibres and thermosetting resin, have a viscoelastic behaviour induced by the properties of the matrix.

N. Laws and R. Mc Laughlin [1] use a self-consistent model to represent the elastic problem and by the intermediary of convolution in the sense of Stieltjes and Carson transforms, they are able to reduce the viscoelastic case to a form equivalent to the elastic problem.

Several authors make the hypothesis that the resin possesses a non-linear viscoelastic behaviour. This is the case of Horoschenkoff [2] who determines the transverse and shear compliances of the composite.

The present study concerns the analysis and modification of the self-consistent model of N. Laws and R. Mc Laughlin based on a comparison with experimental data. The initial model has been modified by several corrections, in particular the viscoelastic non-linearity of the resin has been taken into account. The problem connected with the interface between the fibre and the matrix will be examined more closely as it is the source of significant differences between theory and experiments and cannot be handled by the self-consistent method.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The model of N. Laws and R. Mc Laughlin

The elastic behaviour of the unidirectional longitudinal composite is described by a 4th order tensor $\underline{\underline{S}}$ relating the stress $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}$ to the strain $\underline{\underline{\epsilon}}$. For the elementary constituents, the same relations

are used. The self-consistent model proposed by N. Laws and R. Mc Laughlin leads, in the elastic case, to a relation between $\underline{\underline{S}}$ and $\underline{\underline{S}}^m$, $\underline{\underline{S}}^f$, c^m and c^f , where c^m and c^f are respectively the volume fractions of the resin and the fibre. The analysis of the viscoelastic behaviour is based on the Stieltjes convolution, which allows the precedent relations to be written in the form :

$$\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}} = \underline{\underline{S}} * \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \quad (1)$$

where $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}(t)$ is given by :

$$\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}(t) = S(t) \cdot \sigma_0 + \int_0^t S(t - \tau) \cdot \frac{d\sigma(\tau)}{d\tau} \cdot d\tau \quad (2)$$

The relations derived in the elastic case thus apply to the viscoelastic case if the Carson transforms of the function are considered instead of the function themselves.

The Carson transform of a function f , denoted \hat{f} , is defined by : given $f(t)$

$$\hat{f}(s) = s \cdot \int_0^{\infty} \exp(-s \cdot t) \cdot f(t) \cdot dt \quad (3)$$

Equation (1) becomes :

$$\hat{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}}(s) = \hat{\underline{\underline{S}}}(s) : \hat{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}}(s) \quad (4)$$

Thus the solution of the viscoelastic problem can be obtained in the time domain by applying the inverse Carson transform. The use of this method is only worthwhile for the hypothesis of a linear viscoelastic resin, taking into account the Boltzmann superposition principle implicitly contained in the Stieltjes convolution. The material employed in this study is unidirectional and constituted of E (Vetrotex) glass fibres and an epoxy resin DGEBA (Ciba Geigy).

The behaviour of the fibres is elastic and isotropic and thus requires two independant characteristics in order to characterize it : Young's modulus E^f and Poisson's ratio ν^f , whose values are respectively 73000 MPa and 0.25.

The behaviour of the resin requires a more thorough examination and is analyzed in the following paragraph.

3. IDENTIFICATION OF THE RESIN

Compression and creep under compression tests have been performed using cylindrical specimens. A linear viscoelastic model is assumed for the resin and thus the relaxation spectrum as well as the relaxed modulus must be sought.

The approximation method of Schwartzl and Staverman [3] is used to show that, for the one hour creep tests, only three relaxation times are active. Taking this remark into account , the uniaxial constitutive equation is assumed to have the following form :

$$\frac{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}(t)}{\sigma_0} = \frac{1}{E_0} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha_i \cdot (1 - \exp(-t / \tau_i)) \quad (5)$$

with τ_i : the relaxation times respectively equal to 10, 100 and 2000 seconds,

E_0 : the initial Young's modulus equal to 3500 MPa,

and α_i : coefficients related to the relaxed modulus.

Based on the experimental data, it is seen that the relaxed modulus depends on the stress thus indicating the presence of non-linear viscoelasticity. In order to retain the relation appropriated

from the model of N. Laws and R. Mc Laughlin, it is proposed to determine the coefficients α_i as functions of the octahedric stress σ_{oct} in the resin :

$$\alpha_i(\sigma_{oct}) = k(\sigma_{oct}) \cdot \alpha_i^{(0)} \quad i = 1, 2 \text{ et } 3 \quad (6)$$

$$\text{with } \sigma_{oct} = \sqrt{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + \sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2 + 6 \cdot \sigma_6^2}$$

A good approximation is obtained for :

$$k(\sigma_{oct}) = 7.7 \cdot 10^{-2} + 6.10^{-4} \cdot \sigma_{oct}^2 \quad (7)$$

From now on, the simulation of the creep tests can be performed and is presented in figure (1).

Figure 1 : simulation of the resin strain versus time.

The results are entirely acceptable and the relative difference between theory and experiments does not exceed 2 %. The measurement of the Poisson's ratio during the course of the tests shows its invariance with respect to time.

The isotropy of the resin thus implies the knowledge of its multiaxial behaviour. Equation (11) can be written in the following tridimensional form :

$$\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}(t) = \underline{\underline{S}} : \underline{\underline{\sigma}} + \sum_{i=1}^3 (1 - \exp(-t / \tau_i)) \cdot \underline{\underline{A}}_i : \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \quad (8)$$

or in the Carson space :

$$\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}(s) = \underline{\underline{S}} : \underline{\underline{\sigma}} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{1}{1 + \tau_i \cdot s} \right) \cdot \underline{\underline{A}}_i : \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \quad (9)$$

The elements of the tensor $\underline{\underline{A}}_i$ are related in a way similar to those obtained for the elastic isotropic tensor $\underline{\underline{S}}^m$ of the resin

Table 1 summarizes the properties of the resin and the fibre :

τ_i (secondes)	10	100	2000
α_i^0 (MPa ⁻¹)	$7.314 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.901 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$4.824 \cdot 10^{-5}$
E^m (MPa)	3500		
ν^m	0.34		
$k^m_{(\sigma oct)}$	$7.7 \cdot 10^{-2} + 6 \cdot 10^{-4} * (\sigma oct)^2$		
$A_{jj}^i(\sigma oct)$ (MPa ⁻¹)	$\alpha_i(\sigma oct)$		
$A_{jl}^i(\sigma oct)$ (MPa ⁻¹)	$-\nu^m * \alpha_i(\sigma oct)$		
$A_{kk}^i(\sigma oct)$ (MPa ⁻¹)	$2 * (1 + \nu^m) * \alpha_i(\sigma oct)$		
E^f (MPa)	73000		
ν^f	0.25		

Table 1 : properties of the resin and the fibre

4. BEHAVIOUR OF THE UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE

The preceding study has demonstrated the non-linear viscoelastic behaviour of the resin. This phenomenon is taken into account in the model of N. Laws and R. Mc Laughlin by expressing the unidirectional behaviour as a function of the stress.

For each stress, the resin will have a linear viscoelastic behaviour described by an equation of the form (8) in which the tensors $\underline{\underline{A}}_i$ will be imposed and whose values will depend on the octahedric stress in the matrix.

DEFINITION OF THE OCTAHEDRIC STRESS

At this point, it is necessary to define the octahedric stress σ_{oct} in the resin at the interior of the composite, and thus the stress state in the resin as a function of the stress state in the composite. Horoschenkoff [2], Lou and Schapery [4] propose a calculation of this stress state based on the invariance of the fibre length, which gives :

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1^m &= \nu^m \cdot \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_2^m &= \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_6^m &= \sigma_6 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

An improvement of this formula can be obtained by accounting for the stiffness of the fibres. If a stress σ_1 is applied, the total strain is written : $\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_1^m = \varepsilon_1^f$; which allows σ_1^m to be determined in the form :

$$\sigma_1^m = \frac{\sigma_1 \cdot E^m}{(c^f \cdot E^f + c^m \cdot E^m)} \quad (11)$$

Hence ;

$$\sigma_{oct} = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \sqrt{(\sigma_1^m - \sigma_2^m)^2 + (\sigma_1^m)^2 + (\sigma_2^m)^2 + 6 \cdot (\sigma_6^m)^2} \quad (12)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1^m &= \nu^m \cdot \sigma_2 + \frac{E^m}{(c^f \cdot E^f + c^m \cdot E^m)} \cdot \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2^m &= \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_6^m &= \sigma_6 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

BEHAVIOUR LAW OF THE COMPOSITE MATERIAL

The equation relating the stress and the strain for the composite in the Carson space is sought in a form similar to that relative to the resin. Hence, a temporal behaviour law is determined which is similar to that obtained for the pure resin :

$$\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}(t) = \underline{\underline{S}} : \underline{\underline{\sigma}}(t) + \sum_{i=1}^3 (1 - \exp(-t / \tau_i)) \cdot \underline{\underline{B}}_i : \underline{\underline{\sigma}}(t) \quad (14)$$

$\underline{\underline{B}}_i$ are tensors which are a function of the octahedric stress in the matrix and thus indirectly of the stress applied to the material. Numerically, only S_{22} , S_{66} and S_{23} depend on time. Since S_{23} does not intervene in a plane stress state, only the evolution of S_{22} and S_{66} will be examined. The tensors $\underline{\underline{B}}_i$ will thus only affect these two compliances.

5. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND DISCUSSION

Compression tests and creep tests under compression have been performed on unidirectional composites. The choice of the compression has been imposed to avoid the early appearance of damage, as in the tensile case along the transverse direction, which is common in plane stress. The three principal loadings for $\theta = 0^\circ$; 45° and 90° have been studied. Recall that θ is the angle between the fibre direction and the tension-compression axis. In the principal orthotropic axes, the stresses are written as a function of a stress σ_x applied along the tension-compression axis, in the following form :

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= \sigma_x \cdot \cos^2(\theta) \\ \sigma_2 &= \sigma_x \cdot \sin^2(\theta) \\ \sigma_6 &= \sigma_x \cdot \sin(\theta) \cdot \cos(\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

A non-negligible difference between the experiment and the theory can be noted, a difference which is even very significant for S_{66} . This naturally leads to a significant error in the predicted viscoelasticity. To take the quality of the fibre-matrix interface into account, the isotropic fibre is replaced by an anisotropic one. This one will be identify so that the elastic properties of the composite are accurate. However, this substitution remains insufficient in the case of shear tests where an elastic non-linearity is observed. This phenomenon has already been noticed by numerous authors such as Hahn and Tsai [5] who obtains the following formula based on considerations related to the definition of the elastic energy :

$$\varepsilon_{66} = S_{66} \cdot \sigma_6 + S_{6666} \cdot \sigma_6^3 \quad (16)$$

Recalling that S_{66} is the value of the classical elastic constant for low stress levels, then S_{6666} is chosen to have the form $\alpha \cdot S_{66}$.

New coefficients of the anisotropic fibre and all of the results are respectively presented in table 2 and 3 :

E_{11} (MPa)	73840
ν_{21}	0.300
ν_{23}	0.198
E_{22} (MPa)	63140
G_{12} (MPa)	17680

Table 2 : characteristics of the anisotropic fibre

S_{11} (MPa ⁻¹)	$2.22 \cdot 10^{-5}$	E_{11} (MPa)	45000
S_{12} (MPa ⁻¹)	$-7.741 \cdot 10^{-6}$	ν_{21}	0.120
S_{23} (MPa ⁻¹)	$-2.24 \cdot 10^{-5}$	ν_{23}	0.347
S_{22} (MPa ⁻¹)	$6.45 \cdot 10^{-5}$	E_{22} (MPa)	15500
S_{66} (MPa ⁻¹)	$1.54 \cdot 10^{-4}$	G_{12} (MPa)	6500
$\alpha (S_{6666})$	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$		

α_{i1}^{22} (MPa ⁻¹)	$1.086 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.874 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.901 \cdot 10^{-6}$
α_{i1}^{66} (MPa ⁻¹)	$1.974 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.541 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.055 \cdot 10^{-5}$

k_{22}	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-2} + 5.37 \cdot 10^{-4} * (\sigma_{oct})^2$
k_{66}	$8.9 \cdot 10^{-2} + 3.74 \cdot 10^{-4} * (\sigma_{oct})^2$
$B_{22} = B_{33}$ (MPa ⁻¹)	$k_{22} * \alpha_{i1}^{22}$

Table 3 : properties of the composite

Now that the model is entirely and correctly identified in the elastic domain, it is possible to simulate the creep tests which were performed on the unidirectional composites at 0° , 90° and 45° . Figures (2) and (3) show the results in the transverse and shear directions, respectively, the latter having been obtained by off-axis tests on the unidirectional composites at 45° . The longitudinal tests have not been presented because almost no creep was observed in this case. However, it can be noted that the simulations described this phenomenon accurately.

Figure (2) shows a perfect correlation between the theory and experiments for the unidirectional composite at 90° . On the other hand, the difference, in the shear case, fluctuates until up to 10 % for different creep stresses.

Figure 2 : simulation of the composite transverse strain versus time.

Figure 3 : simulation of the composite shear strain versus time.

CONCLUSION

The self-consistent model of N.Laws and R. Mc Laughlin have been improved to take into account the non-linearity of the matrix and a weak interface between the fibre and the matrix. The last point was solved by considering an anisotropic behaviour for the fibre.

The proposed method allows the viscoelasticity of the resin to be characterized and a few simple and rapid tensile-compression tests on unidirectional composites allow the global viscoelastic behaviour of this composite to be determined with a correct precision.

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